

ANTIOXIDANT, ANTIDIABETIC AND ANTICANCER PROPERTIES OF KABASURA KUDINEER: INSIGHTS INTO ITS THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL

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ABSTRACT

Kabasura Kudineer, a traditional Siddha medicine was analysed for their health benefits. The methanol extract of Kabasura Kudineer was analysed for phytoconstituents and evaluated for antioxidant activity using 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl and 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) assays. Its inhibitory effects on α -amylase and α -glucosidase enzymes were determined using standard protocols. The extract's cytotoxicity against A549 cancer cells was assessed via 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide assay, and morphological changes in treated cells were observed. Phytochemical analysis confirmed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and saponins in the extract. Kabasura Kudineer extract exhibited significant antioxidant activity, inhibited α -amylase and α -glucosidase enzymes, showed cytotoxicity against A549 cells. Morphological changes observed in treated cells suggested induction of apoptosis.

KEYWORDS: Anticancer properties, Antidiabetic effects, Antioxidant activity, Kabasura Kudineer.

INTRODUCTION

Kabasura Kudineer is a traditional Siddha medicine formulation originating from the ancient Siddha system of medicine, which has its roots in South India, particularly Tamil Nadu. It is known for its potential in boosting immunity and aiding in the management of respiratory ailments, especially during times of infections like cold, cough, and fever (Shanmugavelu 2003). It is a polyherbal preparation consisting of 15 herbs, including *Zingiber officinale*, *Piper Longum*, *Syzygium aromaticum*, *Anacyclus pyrethrum*, *Tragia involucrata*, *Hygrophila auriculata*, *Terminalia chebula*, *Justicia adhatoda*, *Plecthranthus amboinicus*, *Costus speciosus*, *Tinospora sinensis*, *Clerodendrum serratum*, *Andrographis paniculata*, *Cyperus rotundus*, and *Cissampelos pareira*. These plants include a variety of bioactive chemicals such as piperine, piperlonguminine, eugenol, stigmasterol, sitosterol, fatty acids and gallic acid (Kiran *et al.*, 2022). These herbs are carefully selected for their therapeutic properties and are believed to work synergistically to provide relief from respiratory symptoms and enhance the body's natural defence mechanisms. Kabasura Kudineer gained significant

attention during the COVID-19 pandemic, with some studies and anecdotal evidence suggesting its potential role in managing symptoms associated with respiratory infections (Natarajan *et al.*, 2021; Khapre *et al.*, 2023). Kabasura Kudineer is reported to have immunomodulatory (Sathiyarajeswaran *et al.*, 2020), antioxidative (Kirithi *et al.*, 2021), antidiabetic (Veeraraghavan *et al.*, 2022), antiviral activity (Kabilan *et al.*, 2022), anticancer activity against A549 (Lung cancer) cells (Nisha *et al.*, 2021; Ashwin *et al.*, 2021), antimicrobial activity (Sujeethasai 2020), antipyretic, anti-inflammatory and antibacterial activity (Saravanan 2018).

Diabetes mellitus is a prevalent metabolic disorder characterized by elevated blood sugar levels due to insufficient insulin activity. With 463 million individuals affected in 2019 and an estimated 700 million projected by 2045, its impact is significant (Saedi *et al.*, 2019). The condition leads to various complications such as retinopathy, nephropathy, neuropathy, peripheral artery disease, cardiovascular disease, and stroke (Rangel *et al.*, 2019). Current treatments involve insulin injections and

oral hypoglycaemic medications like metformin, acarbose, sitagliptin, and glimepiride. However, these medications often have adverse effects such as gastrointestinal distress, diarrhoea, pancreatitis, and congestive heart failure (Akhtar *et al.*, 2022), leading to poor adherence among patients due to both side effects and high costs (Polonsky *et al.*, 2016). As a result, research into natural alternative treatments for diabetes mellitus has surged in recent years, reflecting a growing interest in finding safer and more affordable options. Diabetes-related oxidative stress leads to complications like inflammation and cell damage (Cecilia *et al.*, 2019). Plants with antioxidant properties offer promising avenues for managing these effects. Traditional plant-based medicines are preferred in many regions for their accessibility and minimal side effects compared to pharmaceuticals. Over 400 plant species show potential for controlling diabetes, driving ongoing research into natural treatments (Malviya *et al.*, 2011). Kabasura Kudineer exhibits significant antidiabetic properties, as demonstrated in vitro through assays on alpha-amylase and alpha-glucosidase activity. The extract displayed significant antidiabetic effects, showing increased alpha-amylase and alpha-glucosidase inhibition in dose dependant manner as compared with healthy group (Harini *et al.*, 2022).

The anticancer activity of Kabasura Kudineer has not been studied extensively. There are few reports of their dose dependant cytotoxic effect against A549 cell lines. The extract was reported to decrease the expression of IL-6, TNF- α , inhibitory kappa B-kinase and mTOR in A549 cell lines as compared to control without treatment (Nisha *et al.*, 2021; Ashwin *et al.*, 2021). Kabasura Kudineer holds promise as a natural, affordable treatment for diabetes and cancer. Its antioxidant properties and ability to modulate key inflammatory and cell signalling pathways may underlie its therapeutic potential.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Kabasura Kudineer powder was purchased from ecommerce website. L6 and A549 cell lines were procured from NCCS, Pune. Ten grams of sample was overnight soaked in 100 ml of methanol on magnetic stirrer followed by filtration and evaporation at room temperature. Dried crude was weighed and diluted in methanol for further analysis.

Phytochemical analysis of extract

Kabasura Kudineer methanolic extract was qualitatively and quantitatively analysed for their phytoconstituents like Alkaloid (Surmaghi *et al.*, 1992), flavonoid (Somolenski *et al.*, 1972), tannins (Segelman, Farnsworth 1969), cardiac glycosides (Ajaiyeobu 2002), steroids (Liebermann-Burchard reaction), saponins (Kappor *et al.*, 1969). Their total phenolic and flavonoid content was estimated following the protocol of Singleton *et al.*, 1999 and Pontis *et al.*, 2014 respectively.

Antioxidant activity of plant extract

For antioxidant assay sample was diluted to 1 mg/ml concentration.

2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay

The extract's antioxidant activity was evaluated using the stable DPPH radical following the protocol of Blois *et al.*, 1958. A 0.3 mM methanolic DPPH solution was added to one ml of various appropriately diluted extracts and quercetin within the range of 10 to 100 μ g/ml and 5 to 30 μ g/ml respectively, followed by 30 minutes incubation in dark. Absorbances were noted at 517 nm. Reagent blank was used as control. DPPH scavenging activity was calculated using the following equation.

$$\% \text{ DPPH scavenging activity} = \left(\frac{\text{Abs control} - \text{Abs sample}}{\text{Abs control}} \right) 100$$

A calibration curve of quercetin and % DPPH scavenging activity was prepared. The IC₅₀ of sample and quercetin was estimated.

2, 2'-azinobis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS) assay

The ABTS test was carried out in accordance with the Pellegrini *et al.*, 1958 methodology. A 1:1 mixture of 2.45 mM potassium persulfate and 7 millimolar (mM) of ABTS in water was added, and the mixture was then incubated in the dark for 12–16 hours. After that, the reagent was diluted to get an absorbance of around 0.7 at 734 nm wavelength. 3.9 ml of the reagent and 0.1 ml of the different dilutions of extract were mixed together and left in the dark for 10 minutes. At 734 nm, absorbance measurements were made. Methanol and ABTS absorbance measurements were used to create a control sample. In parallel, a quercetin standard curve was produced with a variety of standard dilutions, ranging from 0.25 to 1.5 μ g/ml. The following formula was used to get the ABTS⁺ scavenging effect (%).

$$\% \text{ ABTS scavenging activity} = \left(\frac{\text{Abs control} - \text{Abs sample}}{\text{Abs control}} \right) 100$$

A calibration curve of quercetin and % ABTS scavenging activity was prepared. The IC₅₀ of sample and quercetin was estimated.

α -amylase inhibition assay

The α -amylase inhibitory activity of the extract was assessed using a standard method of Ademiluyi & Oboh, 2013 with slight modifications. In a 96-well plate, a reaction mixture containing phosphate buffer (100 mM, pH 6.8), α -amylase enzyme (2 U/ml), and varying concentrations of extract (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, and 0.5 mg/ml) was preincubated at 37°C for 20 minutes. Then, 0.1 ml of soluble starch (1% in 100 mM phosphate buffer, pH 6.8) was added as a substrate and further incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes. Following this, DNS reagent (100 μ l) was added, and the mixture was boiled for 10 minutes. The absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 540 nm in microplate reader. Acarbose, at concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 0.5 mg/ml, served

as the standard. Control samples without the test substances were included for comparison, and each experiment was conducted in triplicate. The percentage inhibition was calculated using the formula.

$$\text{Inhibitory activity (\%)} = \left(\frac{1 - A_s}{A_c} \right) * 100$$

where A_s is the absorbance in the presence of the test substance and A_c is the absorbance of the control.

α -glucosidase inhibition assay

The extract's α -glucosidase inhibitory potential was evaluated using the Shai *et al.*, 2011 technique. A reaction mixture was preincubated for 15 minutes at 37°C in a 96-well plate. It contained 20 μ l extract and 50 μ l phosphate buffer at various doses (0.1–0.5 mg/l). After the addition of 20 μ l (5 mM) of P-NPG to the substrate, the mixture was maintained at 37°C for a further 20 minutes, 0.1 M Na_2CO_3 solution (50 μ l) was added to terminate the reaction. Acarbose was used at various concentrations for a positive control experiment: 0.1 to 0.5 mg/ml dose range. Absorbances were noted at 540 nm and the formula for calculating the percentage of α -glucosidase inhibition was calculated as.

$$\text{Inhibitory activity (\%)} = \left(\frac{1 - A_s}{A_c} \right) * 100$$

where A_s is the absorbance in the presence of the test substance and A_c is the absorbance of the control.

Subculturing of L6 myoblast Cells

L6 cell lines were sub-cultured in α -MEM containing 10% (v/v) FBS, 50-100 μ l of 10000 U/mL penicillin-streptomycin solution and incubated in 5% CO_2 at 37°C. L6 cells were trypsinized and sub-cultured on reaching 70-80% confluency and maintained till experiment. Cells were deprived of serum 2 hours prior to experiment.

Glucose uptake assay in cells

In L6 cells, the glucose absorption assay was determined using the Gupta *et al.*, 2009 technique. L6 cells were sub-cultured on 6-well plates and kept in a CO_2 incubator at 37°C for 48 hours. After a semi-confluent monolayer had grown, the culture was refreshed in a CO_2 incubator at 37°C for 18 hours using serum-free DMEM containing 0.2% BSA. The medium was thrown away after 18 hours, and the cells were once again cleaned with KRP buffer. Acarbose and Kabasura Kudineer methanolic extract were applied to the cells at several doses (10 to 100 μ g/ml), and 0.1 ml of 1M glucose was added. The cells were then incubated for 30 minutes. The cells were washed three times with 1 ml of ice-cold KRP buffer to stop glucose absorption, and the supernatant was collected for glucose measurements. Three cycles of freezing and thawing were then used to lyse the cells. To estimate the amount of glucose, cell lysate was obtained. Using the GOD-POD technique, glucose absorption was determined as the difference between the starting and end glucose contents in the incubated medium, as follows: Combine 1 ml of reagent with 10 μ l of sample,

then incubate for 25 minutes at 15 to 25°C or 10 minutes at 37°C. Within 60 minutes, measure the absorbance of the sample and the standard against the reagent blank. Glucose concentration under different treatment was estimated using the following equation.

$$\text{Glucose concentration (mmol/L)} = \left(\frac{A_{\text{sample}}}{A_{\text{std}}} \right) * 0.0555 * \text{Concentration of std.}$$

Where 0.0555 is conversion factor, Concentration of glucose is (100 mmol/L)

$$\text{Glucose concentration (mmol/L)} = \left(\frac{A_{\text{sample}}}{A_{\text{std}}} \right) * 55.5$$

To convert mmol/L to mg/dl divide mmol/L by 0.0555

$$\text{Glucose concentration (mg/dl)} = \frac{\left(\frac{A_{\text{sample}}}{A_{\text{std}}} \right) * 55.5}{\left(\frac{A_{\text{sample}}}{A_{\text{std}}} \right) * 0.0555}$$

Or

$$\text{Glucose concentration (mg/dl)} = \left(\frac{A_{\text{sample}}}{A_{\text{std}}} \right) * 100$$

Where A_{sample} is absorbance of sample and A_{std} is absorbance of acarbose standard

Cytotoxicity assay against cancer cell line

Cell cytotoxicity and the IC₅₀ of the crude extract of Kabasura kudineer were evaluated according to the protocol of Mosmann, 1983. 0.1 ml A549 cells were incubated with different dilutions of the crude extract from 0.01 to 0.2 mg/ml for 24 hours in a CO_2 incubator at 37°C, 5% CO_2 , and 95% humidity. One well served as a cell control and contained only cells and no extract, while two wells were negative controls, having only DMSO and media. After 24 hours of incubation, the supernatant was discarded, and then 25 μ l of MTT (5 mg/ml) was added to each well, followed by 2 hours of incubation at 37 °C in a CO_2 incubator. Each well received 100 μ l of DMSO and was shaken for 15 minutes, followed by absorbance at 490 nm. The percentage of cell cytotoxicity was estimated using the following formula.

$$\% \text{ Cell cytotoxicity} = \left(\frac{\text{Cell control} - \text{Cell treated}}{\text{Cell control}} \right) * 100$$

IC₅₀ was calculated from a log curve equation obtained by plotting a graph between log of concentration of extracts and % cell viability.

Evaluation of morphological changes in cells after IC₅₀ treatment

A549 cells of $2 * 10^6$ cells/ml were added to a six-well microplate. IC₅₀ concentration of extract were administered in each well, followed by incubation periods of 24, 48, and 72 hours. Simultaneously cells without treatment were also set for each respective incubation duration. Following a specific day of incubation, the cells were observed using an inverted microscope to detect any changes in their morphology.

Cells were than trypsinized and proceeded for cell count by trypan blue method of cell exclusion.

Statistical analysis

In the present study, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to observed statistical significance between groups and was determined using Duncan's multiple range test. The significance thresholds were considered at the $P < 0.05$ level.

Table 1: Qualitative analysis of phytoconstituents. –ve: absent, +ve: slightly present, ++ve: moderately present, +++ve: strongly present.

Sample	Extract	Phenol	Alkaloid (Wagner's test)	Flavonoid	Tannins	Steroids	Saponins
Kabaseer Kudineer powder	Methanol	++ve	+++ve	++ve	+ve	-ve	+ve

These findings are following previous studies on Kabasura Kudineer and suggest the powder possesses a range of pharmacological properties like anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-viral, and immunomodulatory effects due to the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and saponins, which are known to exhibit these activities (Mekala *et al.*, 2020). Steroids are more commonly found in plants from the Solanaceae and Asteraceae families (Kiran *et al.*, 2022).

Antioxidant activity of plant extract

Kabasura kudineer is a polyherbal Siddha formulation used in traditional Indian medicine. The methanolic extract of Kabasura kudineer demonstrated DPPH and ABTS radical scavenging activity. For DPPH inhibition,

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemical analysis of extract

The phytochemical analysis of Kabasura Kudineer powder methanol extract revealed the presence of several important bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and saponins, while steroids were not detected (Table 1) (Pakkirisamy *et al.*, 2021; Kiran *et al.*, 2022).

at 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, the extract inhibited 19.38% of DPPH radicals, which goes up to 78.70% at 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, and for ABTS inhibition, at 1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, the extract inhibited 25.14% of ABTS radicals, and the inhibition increased to 85.52% at 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Figure 1). The extract was found to have more antioxidant activity against ABTS than DPPH at similar concentrations. The anti-oxidant activity of the extract increased in a dose-dependent manner, and the findings are in accordance with previous results (Pakkirisamy *et al.*, 2021). The antioxidant potential of Kabasura kudineer could be attributed to the presence of various bioactive compounds in the polyherbal formulation. Half maximal concentration to inhibit 50% of DPPH and ABTS free radicals was found to be 57.98 and 4.14 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively indicating its higher potential toward ABTS free radicals.

Figure 1: Antioxidant activity of kabasura kudineer methanolic extract. A: DPPH scavenging activity of quercetin, B: DPPH scavenging activity of kabasura kudineer methanolic extract, C: IC50 of extract and quercetin to scavenge 50% of DPPH free radical, D: ABTS scavenging activity of quercetin, E: ABTS scavenging activity of kabasura kudineer methanolic extract, F: IC50 of extract and quercetin to scavenge 50% of ABTS free radical. All the values are represented as mean \pm std deviation. * and **** indicate level of significance where *** represent $p < 0.001$ and **** indicate $p < 0.0001$.**

α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibition

The effect of the Kabasura kudineer methanolic extract on the inhibitory activity of α -amylase and α -glucosidase are shown in Figure 2. The standard acarbose was used as an antihyperglycemic agent to compare the inhibitory effects of extract. The inhibitory effect of extract (0.1–0.5 mg/ml) against α -amylase and α -glucosidase exhibited dose-dependent activity ($R^2 = 0.9769$ and 0.8034 respectively). Kabasura Kudineer exhibits a progressive rise in the percentage of α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibition at higher concentrations, to 72.22% and 74.23%, respectively, at 500 μ g/ml. Half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) of extract that inhibited 50% of α -amylase and 50 % of α -glucosidase activity was found to be 356.83 μ g/ml and 243.55 μ g/ml

respectively while that of acarbose was found to be 210.06 μ g/ml and 117.01 μ g/ml respectively (Figure 2). Extract showed dose dependant inhibitory activity from 300 μ g/ml concentration. Result obtained is similar to findings of Harini *et al.*, 2022. Kabasura kudineer methanolic extract have been reported to decrease rat paw edema volume by 55.8% in carrageenan induced wistar rat (Jayaram *et al.*, 2018). Anti-inflammatory properties of Kabasura kudineer extract is due to bioactive compounds present in poly herbal formulation and can **reduce the inflammatory responses caused by diabetes. Kabasura Kudineer may have potential as a natural remedy for managing diabetes by inhibiting key enzymes involved in carbohydrate metabolism.**

Figure 2: α -amylase and α -glucosidase activity of Kabasura kudineer methanolic extract. A: α -amylase inhibition activity of Kabasura kudineer methanolic extract and acarbose, B: α -glucosidase inhibition activity of Kabasura kudineer methanolic extract and acarbose, C: IC₅₀ of Kabasura kudineer methanolic extract and acarbose for 50% α -amylase inhibition, D: IC₅₀ of Kabasura kudineer methanolic extract and acarbose for 50% α -glucosidase inhibition. Data are represented as mean \pm std. deviation. Where a, b, c are significance level within group while *,** and *** represent significance level between two groups. * Represents $p < 0.05$; ** indicates $p < 0.01$; and *** $p < 0.001$.

Effect of Kabasura kudineer methanolic extract on Glucose Uptake in L6Cells

The comparative analysis of glucose levels or uptake percentages under the influence of acarbose and Kabasura Kudineer methanolic extract was estimate. Acarbose increased glucose levels initially peaking at 83.51 mmol/L, and then decrease to 72.23 mmol/L (Figure 3), indicating a fluctuating effect on glucose levels. This fluctuation might be due to the drug's mechanism of slowing carbohydrate digestion, which can vary depending on factors such as dosage and individual metabolic responses. In contrast, Kabasura Kudineer methanolic extract exhibits a steady increase in glucose levels, rising consistently from 7.60 mmol/L to 77.37

mmol/L (Figure 3). This suggests a more stable effect on glucose metabolism compared to Acarbose. Kabasura Kudineer's consistent impact may indicate a stable mechanism of action, which could be beneficial for managing glucose levels more predictably. Kabasura Kudineer methanolic extract exhibits significant cytotoxicity towards L6 cells, with cell viability dropping from 72.12% at 10 μ g/ml to 51.06% at 100 μ g/ml (Figure 3B). In contrast, Acarbose has a much milder cytotoxic effect, with cell viability decreasing gradually from 91.82% at 10 μ g/ml to 73.36% at 100 μ g/ml (Figure 3B). While Kabasura Kudineer may offer therapeutic potential, its higher cytotoxicity at elevated concentrations poses a significant concern.

Figure 3: A: Effect of methanolic extract of Kabasura kudineer polyherbal formulation on glucose uptake in L-6 cell line. B: % Cell viability in L6 cell treated by acarbose and extract. Data are represented as mean \pm std. deviation. Where a, b, c, d, e are significance level within group while there is no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between two groups.

Cytotoxicity assay against A549 cancer cell line

Methanol extract of Kabasura Kudineer on A549 cell lines showed a marked dose-dependent effect; cytotoxicity increased from 44.41% at 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ to almost 90% at 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Figure 4), indicating high potential to kill cancer cell. Previous studies have shown

that the extract was effective at doses between 300-400 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ after incubation for 48 hours (Nisha *et al.*, 2021). The methanolic extract of Kabasura Kudineer was found have an IC_{50} value of about $12.3 \pm 0.68 \mu\text{g/ml}$ (half maximal inhibitory concentration), capable of killing half the population of cancerous cells present in the body.

Figure 4: % Cell Cytotoxicity of Kabasura kudineer methanolic extract on A549 cancer cell lines. Data are represented as mean \pm std. deviation.

Morphological changes in cells after IC_{50} treatment

Morphological analysis of A549 cells treated with IC_{50} concentration showed significant changes after 48 and 72 hrs. of incubation. After 48 hrs. cells become round and less in numbers indicating early onset of apoptosis (Figure 5). Kabasura Kudineer methanolic extract has shown to inhibit the proliferation of A549 lung cancer cells. With increase in time of incubation, cell counts in the control group increased indicating a normal growth of cells while that of treatment group decreased showing

that the extract was able to slow down and stop the multiplication of these cancerous cells.

Figure 5: Morphological analysis and cell count of cells after IC₅₀ treatment at different time of incubation. A: A549 cell control without any treatment after 72 hrs. B: IC₅₀ concentration of extract treated A549 cells after 24 hrs. C: IC₅₀ concentration of extract treated A549 cells after 48 hrs. D: IC₅₀ concentration of extract treated A549 cells after 72 hrs. E: Cell count at different time of incubation. Data are represented as mean \pm std dev.

CONCLUSION

Kabasura Kudineer, a polyherbal formulation rooted in traditional Indian medicine, exhibits a broad spectrum of pharmacological benefits. Its methanol extract contains alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and saponins, contributing to its diverse therapeutic properties such as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, antiviral, and immunomodulatory effects. These bioactive compounds confer potent antioxidant activity against DPPH and ABTS radicals, suggesting potential applications in combating oxidative stress-related disorders. Moreover, Kabasura Kudineer demonstrates significant inhibitory effects on α -amylase and α -glucosidase enzymes, crucial in managing blood glucose levels and potentially offering benefits in diabetes management. Additionally, its observed cytotoxic effects on A549 cancer cells underscore its potential in cancer treatment, supported by morphological changes indicative of apoptosis induction. While these findings highlight Kabasura Kudineer's promising therapeutic potential, further studies are essential to explore its safety profile, optimize dosage, and validate its efficacy in clinical settings for broader therapeutic use.

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